

Re-users first: designing openly licensed MOOCs to enable adaptation

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Abstract. This paper will introduce the MOOC “Enhancing Education through Open Opportunities” as an opportunity the authors took to prioritise re-users and offer an effective learning experience intentionally.

Open Education (OE) is reshaping learning methodologies through practices that build on each other intentionally. The MOOC “Enhancing Education through Open Opportunities” puts re-users first, together with learners, and aims to be a valuable resource for educators, instructional designers, and practitioners seeking to explore and implement open educational practices. Hosted on the Polimi Open Knowledge (POK) platform, the course is part of the “MOOCs for Teachers” series. The learning experience it offers emphasises sharing, improving, and re-using educational content, enabling knowledge dissemination across diverse learning environments.

Beyond content accessibility, the MOOC fosters a participatory culture in education, encouraging practitioners to explore open solutions and engage with decision-makers in advocating for sustainable educational change. Examining real-world open education examples across multiple disciplines and educational levels, participants are inspired to innovate and implement open practices tailored to their unique challenges.

The paper will provide a walkthrough of the adaptation process, illustrating how users can modify content using open-source tools with minimal technical skills. Participants will gain insights into best practices for customising materials while maintaining pedagogical integrity and instructional effectiveness.

Through developing and managing this MOOC project, valuable lessons were learned regarding effective project organisation and communication, which this paper describes.

Keywords: Open Educational Resources, Reuse, Adaptation, Open Process, Open Software, Open Licences.

1 “Open” as an intentional choice

1.1 How can a Massive Open Online Course be really “Open”?

“Open” is a different approach to education. Its focus is on sharing, improving, and reusing educational materials created by people (teachers, content experts, librarians,

practitioners; sometimes students themselves are involved and not only super-experts) who are willing to let knowledge spread and be used by anyone. This intentional choice and its consequences enable others to tailor the resources and practices to their contextual needs.

According to the Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary & Thesaurus, the acronym MOOC is the "abbreviation for massive open online course: a course of study that is made available over the internet and a large number of people can follow that". The word "open" means freely accessible to anyone [1]. Since 2008 free MOOCs have transformed access to education, benefitting learners of all ages [7].

In the realm of Open Education, the word "open" means more than just freely accessible to anyone: it means free plus the permissions provided by the open licences associated with the resources [9]. One of the most common types of open licences is represented by the Creative Commons licenses [2].

In this paper, we describe the work done to make a MOOC intentionally as open as possible, enabling reuse and adaptation through more than a CC license: an open process, multiple open formats, the choice of open software only, and a radical knowledge-sharing approach.

1.2 A radically open MOOC in the making

The MOOC "Enhancing education through open opportunities" is hosted on the Polimi Open Knowledge (POK) platform [6] as part of the "MOOCs for Teachers" series and serves as a valuable resource for educators, instructional designers, and practitioners seeking to explore and implement open educational practices.

The MOOC was designed by a team of staff members with different professional profiles working at METID, the task force for learning innovation of Politecnico di Milano. The authors of this paper are part of the staff involved in the design and implementation of this MOOC. It aims to help practitioners, instructional designers, teachers, and librarians build on their existing knowledge and skills, thanks to reusable opportunities from open education examples in different fields and at different levels, as well as by exploring diverse formats. It also aims to inspire them with a diverse range of experiences: participants are invited to explore those examples that relate more directly to their contextual needs. After attending the MOOC, participants are also invited to consider approaching and dialoguing with decision-makers to experiment with open solutions and, through them, ignite and fasten change for a better impact on shared societal challenges.

1.3 Radical openness to enable reuse and adaptation

As a team of instructional designers and developers, we used this opportunity to experiment with radical openness and consider re-users as our main target group, together with participants of the MOOC itself. The MOOC was designed for easy reuse and adaptation without proprietary software.

Thanks to the open approach of our managing director, Susanna Sancassani, we could explore widely and wildly how to adapt the production process to these priorities.

This was the first experience with a design process based on radical openness to prioritise enabling, reuse and adaptation: we had to compromise to prioritise ease of adaptation at the macro, meso, and micro levels. As a result, the complete MOOC dataset in editable format is now available on Zenodo [4], shared with a CC BY licence.

2 The design process for open content: different perspectives

2.1 The instructional design approach to enable reuse intentionally

As stated in the MOOC description, the learning path is designed for people involved in education at all levels: teachers, students, instructional designers, librarians, and content editors.

During the pre-design phase, we started discussing the option of testing the creation of an open MOOC to enable re-users at best, even when they have no other resources except their time and expertise. We wanted to share knowledge in the most reusable way and experiment with what it means in terms of human resources and work processes. This initial discussion involved the Managing Director of the Teaching and Learning Innovation Task Force, the project manager and the instructional designer.

It is a cost for a unit like ours to test a different process to work on MOOCs: we have a very efficient and effective process in place, tested across over 140 MOOCs so far, and we use professional software under a licence. Using only open-source software to let anyone open editable versions of all files so that they can potentially adapt each detail means drastically creating a new process and using new tools. To effectively explore the open-source tools that could best enable us to do quality work with the formats we need, the project manager, the video editor and the graphic designer tested multiple options with different perspectives and prioritised across necessary compromises while designing the most effective learning experience we could provide.

We then explored sources of openly licenced, reusable, and adaptable elements in all areas, including graphic elements, templates and parts of broader content. Since not all teams have the privilege to have all the professional profiles and skills we have, we wanted to intentionally ensure re-users are in the best possible position not to invent or create anything already available if they don't have the expertise - or the time needed to learn and explore - so they can focus on the key elements of the learning path.

The team collaborated to balance priorities for optimal reuse: time and budget are always limited, even in the most privileged contexts, and avoiding wasting resources (even more, if public) was one of our priorities to be consistent. We were now ready to start designing the MOOC index according to intended learning outcomes, assessment strategy, and content.

So we chose a diverse range of reusable resources that were consistent with the purpose, the approach, and the focus to test the challenges across the production path. The more diverse the licences and resources were, the better - this action was done on purpose to stress the process since this was a pilot; generally speaking, the challenges would arise during the process AFTER the choice of resources that fit for purpose. Here and there, we had to consider changing the format of specific content, taking reuse into account/as a priority despite the best option in terms of visual quality.

Another choice we made intentionally was to add links to reused and adapted graphic and content elements in the slides (which were the format needed for the keywords and graphic elements of the videos) even if the links were not going to be active when visualised in the videos. We wanted to make the links easily verifiable when reused and with a well-written TASL attribution statement (Title, Author, Source, Licence) [3] and to enable the reuse and adaptation of the slides as a stand-alone OER that could be enhanced with a textual explanation in case the video is not the ideal option in the reuse context. Additional effort was made to create and share instructions for re-users, collected in the last section of the MOOC and on Zenodo.

Certain file types need an explanation about the whys and hows to enable reuse and adaptation experiences at best. We made the choices; we had our reasons: sharing the decision-making process was light additional work but could be extremely useful for others to make their own choices more intentionally, whichever their role in the adaptation process. In the design of the assessment phase, we chose to prioritise exercise types that are consistent with more than one platform and easy to adapt.

Even if effective, some exercise formats might be hard to reuse on multiple platforms. We avoided them. As far as an alternative was available and we were not affecting the effectiveness of the exercise, we chose formats and structures that were easy to adapt.

2.2 Technical choices for the visual designer's expertise

The MOOC visual learning designers had to question every aspect of the production in light of the principles of openness and the prospect of enabling others to reuse and remix a complex artefact like a MOOC.

An optimal way to convey the right stream of information through a video lesson is to provide media that aggregates filmed content and graphical contributions such as text, schemes, illustrations, and pictures. Starting from the choice of the software to create videos, we use proprietary software daily, but the objective of providing an entirely editable and remixable MOOC guided us to Open Shot Video Editor by OpenShot Studio [5], an open-source video editing software with a simple interface and low power requirements. This software also has a solid and supportive community to respond quickly to requests. The decision of which software to use cascaded the rest of the process.

Open Shot does not have a built-in graphics editor, so every part of the graphic was made in a third software. The solution we chose was to develop the whole graphic in an open presentation software. The software choice fell to LibreOffice, a suite developed in 2010 by The Document Foundation [8]. It adopts Open Document formats natively and is, of course, available for free and from an open source. Also, LibreOffice IMpress allows the collection of various input file formats so that anyone who is not an expert can insert various genres of multimedia without necessarily having to convert or adapt them.

The visual designers developed a coherent graphic language, providing a template with guidelines that could adapt to nearly every scenario we would encounter. This meant having a modular graphic that would be assembled in a specific way for the

development of the MOOC but could also be easily understood and - partially or entirely - changed by everyone in the future. Then, the content expert took over and developed every specific view. This allowed the visual designers to follow the graphics development from the content experts' point of view and their own as visual designers.

Each slide was based on the space occupied by the lecturer in the video, which changed according to the graphic content's importance, complexity, and readability but was also influenced by the ongoing speech.

While colours are free to everyone, we cannot say the same about letters. The choice of colours for the graphic design was shaped around the rules of readability and contrast. Choosing a font required more attention. We chose an open-licensed font distributed with a SIL Open Font Licence 1.1. The font, named Space Grotesk, comes in five weights and supports 520 languages, which is a great plus for a future translation.

Up to this point, we have laid out the visual foundation and technical constraints necessary for producing each video in the series. After this pre-production phase, the next step was recording and editing, which again involved all the actors in this project firsthand.

2.3 Recording videos to enable adaptation

Having established the project's visual design, we transitioned to the recording phase. We deliberately opted for a straightforward approach: to ensure easy replicability and editing, we recorded each lecture segment in a simple setting reminiscent of a well-lit room or office. We believe this method is easily accessible to many: prioritise high-quality audio and lecturer clarity while maintaining a professional look, even with readily available tools like a smartphone and a dedicated microphone.

With all MOOC footage captured and graphical content compiled as LibreOffice Impress presentations, we moved on to editing. Each slide was exported as a PNG file, framing a transparent area for the lecturer. In OpenShot, we conducted a preliminary edit to remove unnecessary footage, then re-imported the refined clips into the final project. Our editing strategy was simple yet effective: the footage was layered beneath each slide and precisely cut to match the lecturer's speech, creating a seamless sequence. After the review, we went live with the main course.

2.4 How to finally share editable content supporting re-users?

It was now time to finalise the sharing of the editable version of the course materials. We looked for an online repository where we could upload our content. Our choice fell to Zenodo, which allowed us to upload zipped files with each lesson, including the video project, in a slightly diminished resolution to fit the purpose and respect the available gigabyte limits.

Zenodo hosts the complete dataset of the MOOC (the final MOOC videos and all source materials, scripts, project files, and pre-edited footage) with a CC BY licence except where otherwise noted. We've also included documents detailing the technical specifications of each element, along with a step-by-step guide elucidating our editing process.

3 Lessons learned and future directions

This MOOC development process underscored key lessons in project organisation, communication, and the challenges of balancing quality with adaptability. The first lesson we learned regards planning: designing for reuse necessitated rethinking traditional MOOC production workflows. The second lesson is related to compromise for simplicity: reducing unnecessary complexity in graphics and formatting improves the opportunities offered to those who want to take over and adapt the content and keep it alive in other contexts. More skills required equals more complexity on the shoulders of reusers. The third lesson is related to how the editable content is shared: while adding clear documentation enhances usability, thanks to detailed instructions for educators and technical staff, the weight and the structure of the archive require additional intentional care.

The design team found it incredibly rewarding to question every facet of production, deliberately emphasising the “openness” of the learning experience while preserving its quality. Several solutions discovered during this process have already proven valuable in other projects, enhancing our work in tangible ways.

The authors are in contact with the Instituto Superior Técnico (a public university in Lisbon, Portugal), which is currently reusing and adapting the MOOC with the support of students, starting from the provided instructions and dataset. So far, there is no issue whatsoever with quickly implementing the whole MOOC and uploading it on their MOOC Técnico platform. Once completed, their feedback will enrich the practice, and we are in constant contact to learn more about any improvements we can implement on both sides.

Moving forward, the insights gained will inform future radically open MOOCs, refining methodologies for balancing openness with instructional effectiveness. By sharing this experience, the project team aims to contribute to broader discussions on sustainable and scalable open education practices.

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